

**Improving food supply in the conditions of innovative economy
issues of applying the experience of foreign countries**

Abstract: this article analyzes the experience of foreign countries in improving food supply in the conditions of innovative economy. In particular, the experiences of countries such as the Russian Federation, African countries, Canada, Great Britain, France, Italy, Bulgaria and Georgia were analyzed and a number of proposals were developed.

Key words: food supply, improvement, outsourcing, foreign experiences, material supply, digitization, entrepreneurship, Armed Forces.

Implementation of material support of the Armed Forces through the use of external sources took place in many countries of the world in different ways and styles. Military outsourcing has completely covered one or another field of military activity in countries with large armies, such as the United States, Canada, Great Britain, France, and Italy.

At this point, it should be emphasized that the implementation of the outsourcing system and the existing mechanisms in the process of its direct organization are interrelated and have similar aspects, principles and laws.

In particular, the application of the outsourcing system in the organization of army supply and the experience of Russia and several Western countries in its implementation serve as a scientific basis for further increasing the efficiency of the outsourcing system in the material supply of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to the analysis of the available data, the Russian Federation (RF) uses the experience of NATO in the implementation of the use of outsourcing services of foreign enterprises in the field of material support of the combat activities of the troops.

Since January 2012, as a result of the defense reforms of the Russian Federation, maintenance and preservation of military settlements, cleaning of relevant areas and residential areas, bathroom-laundry service and individual tailoring of uniforms, as well as repair of military vehicles and combat equipment. and outsourced part of the service and catering functions to external companies. The practical experience of the Russian Federation was introduced to feed the troops in order to free the army from non-specific tasks.

At the same time, the current situation demands the implementation of necessary reforms to eliminate existing difficulties and shortcomings in order to achieve the intended goal of outsourcing. Most of the major problems in the outsourcing implementation system were mentioned at the collegial meeting of the Ministry of Defense of the Russian Federation.

The first problem is the sharp increase in budget expenditures as the main problem (increased by 50 billion rubles per year).

The second problem is the non-transparency of outsourcing enterprises (outsourcers) and their activities, as well as the lack of unified systematic control over them. The influence of the Ministry of Defense on the control of the outsourcing system is limited only by its participation in the elections to the Board of Directors, which does not affect the operation of the system in a practical way.

The next, third problem is the low quality of services, which is mainly found in the cleaning system and the fact that several business entities perform outsourcing activities in a tiered (intermediary, intermediary) form. The number of intermediary enterprises, which are especially common in the field of transport, has reached 5-8. That is why the Ministry of Defense is currently involved in lawsuits with many enterprises (1 billion rubles on average).

The fourth problem is the slowness of the operational speed of the units of the "Oboronservis" JSC. Business activity should be interested in increasing speed and shortening the execution time of issues that need to be implemented. In practice, it is the opposite.

It can be safely said that in some cases, the certification of completed work takes up to 1-2 years. At the same time, the quality of services is not improving, ultimately, an increase in receivables and payables was observed.

As of August 19, 2014, the state of indebtedness to service providers is 90 billion. reached 100,000 rubles, and domestic debts for monthly salaries amounted to nearly 1 billion rubles.

There is no other view of the current state. After that, according to the instructions of the leadership of the Ministry of Defense, a number of scientists and experts were given the task of publicly pondering over this problematic situation and developing appropriate solutions for ways out of it.

Without abandoning the outsourcing system (the issue of exemption from non-specific tasks for the army worked), solutions to achieve its effective results began to be sought.

"Oboronservis" holding will be completed with the existing 9 subholdings and replaced by 4 subholdings that include construction and communal services, repair production, trade and household services and supply, communication and telecommunication services. they spent After that, the holding was renamed "Garrison" JSC.

The existing subholding "Oboronsstroy" was formed as a single subholding providing construction and utility services. In the structural structure of this subholding, in addition to housing and communal services, a single production and transport logistics center was opened at the base of the "1470-material and technical supply department" OAK.

This center consists of transport logistics complexes located in the districts, which provide for the implementation of material supply and logistics directly in all districts.

The need for the creation of this structure arose due to the real situation in the tactical training of the troops and the need to move troops, personnel, and material resources from one area to another.

In general, the most important attention was paid to the unified management system in the effective organization of the activities of "Garrison" OAC in the quality and timely implementation of material supply through outsourcing.

They included, first of all, the development of the issues of introducing a unified approach to the use of material means and products.

The second was the issue of coordination of corporate organizations and their activities within the corporate holding. The tasks of each subholding were clearly defined, as well as a schedule of corporate activities for the reorganization of "Oboronservis" was drawn up.

In December 2014, "Oboronservis" JSC was completely reorganized into "Garrison" JSC. In the course of the above reforms, no changes were made to the personnel in the block of

providing household services and catering. "Slavyanka" JSC hotel services were handed over to "Garrison" JSC "Voentorg" JSC.

In order to ensure the implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Russian Federation dated January 24, 2013, in order to carry out a unified state policy on the development, production, maintenance, repair and destruction of military and special equipment developments. integration of repair structures and the Defense Industry Complex was carried out.

Reforms in the organization of the subholding for the provision of communication and telecommunication services were transferred from the main shareholder "Voentelekom" OAC to "Garrison" OAC.

Currently, the situation is fundamentally changing. A special investment block of JSC "Garrison" is being established. Enterprises of the investment block do not implement state orders and, in their own way, carry out development activities independently, not as a structural structure of the CEC.

Another unique aspect of this unit's activity is that it produces a strategy with reasonable proposals for the leadership on the effective use of all assets and their rational use, without repeating the old mistakes in the organization of material support of the Armed Forces. In addition, they will develop future plans for the use of the material and technical equipment of the Ministry of Defense, which will be of economic benefit, and make appropriate proposals.

As a result of the implemented reforms, significant positive changes in the volume of work and its quality have been achieved in the outsourcing system of material supply organization.

Up to now, up to 50% of the total work planned in the previous "Oboronservis" is being carried out effectively up to 100% of the types of supplies received separately through "Voentorg". That is, "Voentorg" JSC conducts activities on the types of planned, promising, specific supply necessary for the Armed Forces.

The work carried out in 2014-2015 brought a positive economic result of about 22 billion rubles at the end of the year.

On March 11, 2019, the Minister of Defense of the Russian Federation, Sergei Shoigu, spoke about the material supply outsourcing system at a meeting of the relevant committee, emphasizing that the system does not justify itself in the activities of units in combat situations. That is, the majority of units in combat operations were not fed on time or completely (including the events of January 2022 in Kazakhstan). that technical equipments that have occurred in the event were not provided with technical services and repairs were not carried out on time, as well as the units providing technical services of the Ministry of Defense are more than external executors brought economic benefits as an argument. In addition, he said that there are also sectors of the system that have justified themselves, and he specifically pointed to the housing and communal sector as an example.

In conclusion, the experience of the implementation of the outsourcing system in the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation shows that as a result of the transfer of non-specific tasks and services to external resources in the organization of the outsourcing system of the material supply of the Armed Forces, the troops In addition to achieving a number of positive results from the point of view of combat training, military and special training, the following negative results also occurred:

- increase in budget expenses;
 - high level of corrupt structure, non-transparency of outsourcing enterprises and their activities, and weak real control over their activities;
 - low quality of service and a large number of joint ventures and their schemes in the organization of outsourcing;
 - increased indebtedness to outsourcers;
- The main reasons for these deficiencies are as follows:
- an insufficient level of regulatory and legal framework;
 - excessive centralization of the management structure in service outsourcing enterprises;
 - slow speed and insufficient legal framework.

As a result of the fundamental reforms carried out to increase the quality and efficiency of outsourcing services, by transforming Oboronservis OAC into Voentorg OAC, the number of partner enterprises in the implementation of the outsourcing system has decreased, the quality of service has increased, and prices have been reduced. Significant economic savings were also achieved.

The work to be carried out in the Russian Federation in the future is being continued by systematic monitoring by "Voentorg" OAC, and periodically analyzing and developing proposals for existing problems and shortcomings. By carrying out these works, in the organization of the material support of the National Guard through the outsourcing system, it is possible to achieve the following in the future:

- attracting large investors in relevant fields;
- simplification of the existing contractual and financial system;
- allows to reduce the cost of services.

As for the essence of the experience of Western countries in this field, outsourcing includes the full implementation of the provision of the Armed Forces at the expense of third-party investment.

Military outsourcing services in Western countries

In the early 1990s, when bipolar military confrontations subsided and military spending decreased, it occurred in the United States and NATO member countries.

Of course, the role of the private sector has gained special importance in developing countries where outsourcing services have been established. In any country where there is little state intervention and management in the economy, the private sector has been the locomotive of the national economy.

Initially, outsourcing relationships developed in continental Europe, with the French and Germans adopting these relationships in a limited way.

Since the 2000s, outsourcing services have been massively developed in all European countries, even in African countries, where, within the framework of the military industrial complex, troop transportation, material and technical support, organization of communication services, training and issues of combat training became one of the most important directions.

Outsourcing in foreign countries is distinguished by its special organizational structure and the uniqueness of its implementation mechanism. That is, outsourcing is a form of public-private partnership between the parties entering into a contract in the course of mutual commerce.

To the question of what are the main differences and similarities between the current state of the experience of the Russian Federation in organizing the material supply of the troops through outsourcing and the systems in foreign armies, first of all, we will look at several examples of the foreign experience of improving the feeding of military personnel through the outsourcing system. we will be able to consider as part of the transition.

For example, in the United States, the Logistics Department of the Ministry of Defense is responsible for the food of the military personnel of the Armed Forces. Organization of meals is carried out by enterprises that have won on the basis of relevant tenders. Armed Forces

Food matters in the Canadian Armed Forces are directly handled by the Directorate of Logistics (J4). The civil business entities that won the open tenders in the respective bases will organize the catering. Meals for military personnel are carried out according to the established procedure in canteens consisting of officers', sergeants', and privates' halls. According to some sources, the cost of one day's food for one military serviceman in the USA and Canada is estimated to be around 8 US dollars (67 thousand soums).

Today, in most kitchens in the British Armed Forces, private enterprises provide outsourcing services based on contracts with the respective commanders of the military units. Officers and non-commissioned officers eat separately in sergeants' canteens and in officers' clubs. It is noteworthy that in the British army, personnel with special knowledge capable of independently preparing food and service work in field conditions are provided for in the organizational structure. For this purpose, they will check the process of eating in the canteen for a certain part of the ground troops and determine the proportional number of service personnel.

The process of feeding personnel in the French Armed Forces is carried out through a network of state and private enterprises under the leadership of the State Trade and Industry Organization "Economat Armed Forces". Contracts for 25-30 years are concluded with enterprises on a legal basis. Free meals are provided to all military personnel in military units, in barrack conditions, as well as to military personnel who are on duty abroad.

In Italy, the provision of food to military personnel of all categories is organized free of charge in the field at the expense of the Ministry of Defense. In everyday conditions, only conscripts are fed free of charge. Regular and contract servicemen eat at their own expense through canteens in the state of the military unit.

There are two main types of feeding in the Italian Armed Forces: one is by bringing ready-made food to the military unit, that is, it is only necessary to heat the food. Food delivery is carried out by local entrepreneurs. The second type is cooking in the kitchen of a military unit, if the infrastructure allows cooking.

There is no need for a daily feeding system in this regard due to the established contractual basis for the implementation of food supply in the Bulgarian Armed Forces. Feeding of military personnel in the Bulgarian Armed Forces is carried out by the logistics division, which includes the activities of the enterprise that won the relevant tenders, which is part of the cooperative joint during combat formations and field exercises.

All military personnel working in combat military units, military schools and training centers of the Armed Forces of Georgia are regularly fed in military canteens of the respective state from three locations. Provision of food products and service in the process of feeding is organized through an outsourcing system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is interesting to say that the modern trends of using external resources in the implementation of material support of the Armed Forces are rapidly expanding their scale and geography, as well as their positive results and importance. It should be mentioned here that the analysis of foreign experience in the provision of outsourcing requires the creation and continuous improvement of the organizational-legal, institutional basis for the regulation of economic relations in this regard.

Based on the unique economic and social situation and conditions of each country, relevant reforms will be carried out in priority areas. The military economy as a component of the national economy is a complex of economic reforms aimed at meeting the needs of the military in terms of increasing its combat capability and providing it. activities should be analyzed and monitored.

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